

A History of Buchla's Musical Instruments

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Mr. Buchla presented and showed some of the fascinating musical instruments that he has created since 1965. We were privileged to have the actual instruments available to see and hear on loan courtesy of Don Buchla, David Kean and the Audities Foundation. The instruments that were shown include:

Thunder (1990)

The first of my MIDI controllers, soon to be reincarnated. Its about 18" wide x 12" deep and mounts on a 3 foot tripod.

Wind (1994)

One of several programming disasters, this is about as far as it ever got. Its roughly 18" square, and can be wall mounted.

Lightning II (1996)

Still in production and going strong. Spectators can play this one. The business end is 6" x 8" and is mounted on a 4 foot tripod.

Marimba Lumina (2000)

About 5 of these gold editions were assembled. But lots of its cousins, the Marimba Lumina 3.5 and 2.5 were built and marketed by Nearfield Systems. This instrument is about 8 feet wide by about 2 feet deep, and is mounted on a 3 1/2 foot high keyboard stand. Joel Davel will demonstrate occasionally.

200e (2004)

The latest synth, this is essentially a re-introduction of the 200 series, but with several advanced facilities. It is an excellent example of the knobs and wires approach to user interface. Spectators can play it. Its about 30" wide by 18" deep and is table mounted.

400 (1982)

This pre-MIDI synth sports an advanced video display, and is still in use. Its 24" wide by 18" deep and is table mounted. It will be occasionally demonstrated.

Sili con cello (ca.1975)

This is the Sili side of a Cello and electronics piece composed for cellist Ami Radunskaya. It has been retuned to work with the voice and offers audience interaction. Its about 24" by 18" and is hung on a wall.

Magic flute (1965)

Reflecting the 60's culture, this is a unique user interface. It is about 4 feet wide by a foot high, and can be hung on a wall.